

Almoqbel et al.

LEGEND

● Human-Computer Interaction	● Internet of Things
● Virtual Reality	● Cloud Computing
● Artificial Intelligence	● Health
● Software Security	● Computer Science Education

Our Contribution

NEW!

Social Issues	Community Involved
Interaction and Engagement	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Accessibility and Inclusivity	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Privacy and Security	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Social Norms and Ethics	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Mental Health and Well-Being	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●

NEW!

Technical Issues	Community Involved
Environment Infrastructure	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Privacy and Security	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Interaction and Usability	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Communication and Network	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●
Rendering and Visualization	● ● ● ● ● ● ● ●